

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE MECHANISM OF FINANCING THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

Kimsanboeva Maftuna Bakhodirovna

Teacher of Tashkent Financial Institute

maftunabahodirovna2525@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6626126>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

higher education system, budget system, education system, education system financing.

ABSTRACT

The analysis and conclusions on ways to improve the mechanism of financing the higher education system in our country

From the first years of independence, our country has been paying great attention to the development of education, science and vocational training. Because without the development of these areas, it is impossible to imagine the huge goals we have set for ourselves.

The development of new and effective forms of financing the development of education in our country requires the use of advanced methods of financing.

In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to introduce new principles of management in the system of higher and secondary special education" dated July 11, 2019 No PP-4391 Given the high demand and financial stability of some bachelor's and master's specialties of educational institutions, it was agreed to transfer them to a system of gradual self-financing.[1]

There is a need to study the experience of advanced and developed countries in this

area and expand it, taking into account the socio-economic conditions of our country.

2. Analysis and discussion of results.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed a decree on the concept of development of the higher education system until 2030. According to him, the tasks are set until 2030. In particular, the coverage of general secondary education graduates with higher education should not exceed 50%. This includes the development of public-private partnerships in higher education, the organization of public and non-governmental higher education institutions in the regions. These measures will increase the coverage of higher education by more than 50% and create a healthy competitive environment in the industry. The National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University are expected to become the flagships of higher education institutions of the country. Extra-budgetary

sources of income of higher education institutions include: paid tuition, paid courses, entrepreneurship, rent, services, sponsorship.

Also, at least 10 higher education institutions in the country are included in the list of the first 1,000 higher education institutions in the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities). In particular, the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University will be included in the list of the top 500 higher education institutions.

The sources of financing of the actions provided by this decree are:

- ☑ Funds of the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- ☑ Funds of the Higher Education Development Fund of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- ☑ Extra-budgetary funds of higher education institutions;
- ☑ Sponsorship of individuals and legal entities;
- ☑ Loans from international financial institutions, foreign countries and other donors, grants;
- ☑ Other sources not prohibited by law.

The transition of universities to self-financing takes into account the high demand and financial stability of the market of educational services for certain

undergraduate and graduate specialties of higher education institutions.

3. Conclusions and suggestions.

Higher education institutions that are transitioning to a self-financing system have the following rights:

- Independent determination of bonuses and other types of financial incentives for employees in order to attract highly qualified specialists and improve the quality of educational services;
- financial incentives and support for gifted students, as well as those in need of social protection;
- maintenance costs, fulfillment of tasks and responsibilities, introduction of innovative forms and methods of training and retraining and advanced training of staff, strengthening the material and technical base, software, modern information and communication tools, training and research laboratories and independent spending of funds for the purchase and publication of consumable laboratory materials (reagents, chemical containers, components, biological materials and other objects), including books, magazines, textbooks;
- Certain types of services for the infrastructure of higher education institutions, including the use of buildings and structures, student housing, sports facilities, their cleaning, repair, maintenance of computer equipment and telecommunications networks and the provision of legal services organization on outsourcing terms.

References:

1. M. Kimsanboeva. Perspective issues of increase of efficiency of educational services and business activity // "Science and Education" Scientific Journal. May 2022/ Volume 3, Issue 5, 1678-1681-b.

2. M.Kimsanboyeva. Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi xarajatlarini moliyalashtirishda davlat byudjetining ahamiyati // // "Science and Education" Scientific Journal. May 2022/ Volume 3, Issue 5, 1607-1613-b.

3. M.Kimsanboyeva. Ways to Effectively Organize the Financing of the Education System // "Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching" Volume 7| March 2022, ISSN: 2795-739X

4.Рахмонов Д. Ўзбекистон ижтимоий соҳани молиялаштиришнинг методологик асосларини такомиллаштириш. Иқтисод фанлари доктори (DSc) даражасини олиш учун диссертация автореферати.Т., 2018. 71-б.;

5.Рахимова У.А. Ўзбекистон олий таълим муассасаларида инновацион фаолиятни ривожлантириш йўллари. Иқтисодиёт фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) даражасини олиш учун диссертация автореферати.Самарканд, 2019. 57-б.